

VOCATIONAL TRAINING IN THE FIELD OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Tashkent is specialized for people with disabilities
Vocational vocational school No. 2, master of production education

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Abstract. *This article describes the effective aspects of vocational training in the field of inclusive education, in inclusive education, children with special educational needs are grouped together with all children according to different abilities for a specific purpose, special education is carried out according to mental and physical appearance, inclusive education reveals the child's abilities and opportunities. detailed information is provided.*

Keywords: *inclusive education, "tailoring", disabled people's rights, Kashkadarya, Fergana, Khorezm, UN Human Rights, L.S. Vygotsky.*

INTRODUCTION

Based on the study of research works on the problem and their scientific analysis, it became clear that the education and educational environment of disabled youth should always be good, moderate, should always be given special attention, should not be left out of the eyes of adults. Eastern thinkers about child education, such as Imam al-Bukhari, Abdukhaliq Gijduvani, Abu Isa Muhammad al-Tirmizi, Ibn Sina, Farabi, Beruni, Mirza Ulug'bek, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Imam Ghazali, Bahovuddin Naqshband, Alisher Navai, Abdullah Avloni, were in the family in their time. His scientific and scientific-pedagogical observations written on the problem of education of youth in society and the problem of pedagogical-psychological approach to its maturity are expressed in unique works that have reached us. Especially in the works of Abu Ali ibn Sina, along with healthy children, there are also recommendations regarding the upbringing of children who need special help. Alloma said that disabled children have the right to receive education along with their peers, emphasizing that they have a stronger interest in learning a profession and learning than others. The analysis of the views of Eastern scientists on the education of the child's personality and the influence of education on their development has been serving as a bright star for the next generation.

In the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 46th session of the UN Human Rights Council, special attention was paid to strategic directions, including the ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. Considering that there are nearly 1 billion people with disabilities worldwide, this is an extremely important initiative.

The urgent tasks are to carry out propaganda about the essence of this initiative, to strengthen parliamentary control in the issues of protection of the rights of persons with disabilities. Protecting the rights and interests of persons with disabilities is a large and multifactorial field. Inclusive education is much broader than formal education. This education deals more with children with learning disabilities. What qualities should an inclusive school teacher and educator in an inclusive kindergarten have? In inclusive education, the teacher's professional skills are the main factor. First of all, the teacher must have an inclusive mindset and take responsibility for the quality of education.

The main criteria for the quality of work of teachers in inclusive education is that the teacher protects and respects the rights of all children, regardless of the students' different categories.

Another quality is cooperation. Because cooperation and exchange of ideas is important for teachers. In order for a teacher to systematically evaluate his activity, improve his qualifications regularly, to work effectively with disciplined and inter-institutional groups of children with special educational needs, it is necessary to have qualities such as the use of leadership and management skills, joint problem solving, and the establishment of comprehensive school cooperation.

It is known that in inclusive education, children with special educational needs are grouped together with all children according to different abilities for a specific purpose. If special education is carried out according to mental and physical appearance, inclusive education is determined according to the child's abilities and capabilities. While special education is taught through special and alternative education programs, inclusive education is taught through a child-centered and customized, guided, inclusive curriculum. An important aspect of inclusive education is that children and teachers learn from each other and solve problems together.

This education should not be one-sided. Family involvement is important in building self-confidence, developing skills and abilities, and encouraging learning from a young age in a child with disabilities. It is also important to work with parents in the process of inclusive education. It is worth noting that it is necessary to explain to parents with special needs that their children have the right to be a part of society, to convey this belief to their minds. Special attention is paid to this issue in the educational system of our country.

An example of this is the President's decision on measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs. According to it, inclusive education will be introduced as a test in one school located in cities and districts of Tashkent city. Primary basic classes for children with special educational needs will be opened in one school located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city. In one vocational school located in Kashkadarya, Fergana and Khorezm regions, specialized groups are organized for 9th grade graduates of specialized educational institutions and children with special educational needs.

EXPERIENCE AND RESULTS

In Tashkent Vocational Vocational School No. 2 for disabled persons, along with teaching the secrets of the profession, the pedagogic team uses all its resources to make them physically healthy, mentally mature, and master their professions in the future. Based on the interest of each student, a professional direction is determined, and theoretical and practical classes are held at a high level by teachers and masters of industrial education. Vocational school has the following directions:

Car repair mechanic

Lathe

Tailor

Carpentry and floor laying worker

Chef-confectioner

Garden and recreation garden and landscaping master

Master of residential and communal economy, electric gas welder

Figure 1.

The activities of pedagogues are intense for the interesting passage of the month of "Sewing" direction, which is held in the educational institution in January. Masters of industrial education N. S. Karimova, Kh. A. The Kholmatovas and their students are preparing samples of creative works for the exhibition.

Figure 2.

Master of production education of students of the 1st stage of Tashkent specialized vocational school No. 2 for persons with disabilities B. B. They are doing the practical part of the

lesson taught by Mominkulov on the topic "Disassembling and assembling a car engine" with great interest.

Figure 3.

Students of the "Electrogas welder" course at the vocational school under the leadership of the masters of production education B.E. Kaldibekov and B.E. Mullagaliev are making good progress in their professions.

Figure 4.

Salimov Farrukhjon, a student of the 35th group of the "Cooking" department of the Tashkent specialized vocational school for persons with disabilities No. 2, won the silver medal in the international athletics Olympiad for disabled people, which was held in Istanbul.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, all conditions are being created for the ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in our country. I believe that the reforms aimed at the development of inclusive education throughout the country will be a practical example of this.

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disabled children have the right to receive education along with their peers, emphasizing that they have a stronger interest in learning a profession and learning than others.

L.S. Vygotsky puts forward the idea that the health of the social environment is of primary importance for children with limited health opportunities. He also likens the development of children with disabilities to a plant with bad roots. "Its thin roots do not adapt to the layers and shape of the nutrient soil. They cannot reach the nutrient layers of the soil on their own, but get into the dry and toxic layer. Such a plant could bloom under suitable conditions, but under normal conditions, it will wither before reaching the peak of development.

Therefore, it is appropriate to develop the educational system taking into account the specific aspects of each nation and people, national traditions, customs, goals and tasks of the state, and the mental and physical development of the students. In the case of children with disabilities, if adults help the child's wishes and aspirations as much as possible without opposing the child's will and independence, the difficulties in the process of forming his personality will disappear by themselves. The appearance of stubbornness, stubbornness, and disobedience in a child with limited abilities is caused by excessive manipulation by adults.

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